

FunGlass
centre for functional and
surface functionalized glass

Book of Abstracts

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Vat Photopolymerization 3D printing of Engineered Silicone Mixtures: Process Strategy to Manufacture High-performance Glass/Ceramic-based Components

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ABSTRACT

Vat photopolymerization 3D printing of engineered silicone mixtures represents an exciting development in additive manufacturing (AM), offering new possibilities for the production of silica-based products with tailored properties and intricate designs. The present investigation is dedicated to manufacturing Sr/Mg-Doped hardystonite ($\text{Ca}_{1.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{Mg}_{0.3}\text{Zn}_{0.7}\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$) bioceramic scaffolds by two different types of vat photopolymerization techniques: masked stereolithography (MSLA; Origin Prusa SL1S SPEED 3D printer, Prusa Research a.s., Prague, Czech Republic), and digital light processing (DLP; Lithoz CeraFab 7500, Lithoz, Vienna, Austria). Challenges in this process include the optimization of digital design, ensuring compatibility of the silicone-photopolymer mixture to achieve the desired phase composition, porosity, and mechanical properties after a suitable heat treatment process, and addressing layer adhesion issues with respect to the specific printers. For comparison purposes, a photocurable slurry prepared from melt-derived glass powder of the same composition was also studied. Both precursors route 3-D printed scaffolds fired at 1000°C, yield hardystonite solid-solution crystal as the main crystal phase with very similar chemical composition as evidenced by X-ray diffraction and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis. Although the implementation of the MSLA reduces printing time, better printing accuracy and high-fidelity structures with a smoother surface were obtained by the DLP-Lithoz printer.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, Stereolithography, Bioceramics, Hardystonite, Sinter-crystallization, Silicone mixture

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Development of high solid-load slurry for Stereolithography 3D printing of yttria-stabilized zirconia electrolytes for SOFCs application

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ABSTRACT

A stereolithography (SLA) 3D printing technique based on the layer-by-layer solidification of a photosensitive ceramic slurry via UV-light exposure is the most promising method in terms of the production of ceramic parts with unique design, high resolution, or fine surface finishing [1]. Generally, a suspension with a high solid loading, low viscosity, and homogeneous dispersion of solid filler is essential to obtain defect-free and ceramic parts with a high-performance [2]. However, the high viscosity of high solid-load slurry and non-uniform densification of printed parts during sintering are a still challenge.

In this study, the homogeneous UV-curable slurries based on 8 mol.% yttria-stabilized zirconia powders with a high solid loading and appropriate rheological properties were prepared and used for SLA-based 3D printing. The effects of a particle size distribution, dispersant concentrations (PEG-400) and solid loading on their rheological properties and densification behaviour were studied. The 8 mol.% yttria-stabilized zirconia powder with a wide particle size distribution in the range of 0.2-1 μm was found suitable for preparation of the UV-curable slurries with solid loading of over 30 vol.%. An optimal dispersant concentration of 3 wt% was found to ensure near-fluid behaviour for the suspensions with solid loading of up to 50 vol%. A slurry with a high solid loading of up to 50 vol%, and a low viscosity of 2 Pa/s at a shear rate of 50 s^{-1} was selected for 3D printing of complex-shape electrolytes. Curing tests revealed that the penetration depth of the suspension was suitable for printing the objects with the layer thickness of 30 μm and sufficient connections between layers. All samples were sintered at an optimized sintering rate in the temperature range of 1300-1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 h. The high solid loading and homogeneity of the suspension promote uniform shrinkage of the defect-free printed samples. These results indicate the potential of SLA-based 3D printing technology in preparation self-supported electrolytes for SOFCs applications.

Keywords: Yttria-stabilized zirconia, SOFCs, Stereolithography, Rheology, Dispersant.

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Immobilization of simulated ^{137}Cs via alkaline activation of waste pharmaceutical glass

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ABSTRACT

A new method of cesium immobilization has been successfully developed using alkali activation of boro-alumino-silicate glass and viscous flow sintering. This sustainable approach involves reused powdered glass from discarded pharmaceutical vials that are treated with a 2.5 M CsOH aqueous solution. The glass powders are suspended in the solution and consolidated at low temperatures (40°C) over 7 days, resulting in condensation reactions at hydrated surface layers. The products from partial glass dissolution combine with Cs⁺ ions to form a boro-pollucite (CsBSi₂O₆) solid solution. The immobilization process involves the formation of a stable gel that binds both the residual glass powder and the newly-formed crystal phase. Further stabilization is achieved through viscous flow sintering at 700 °C, with Cs⁺ ions dispersed in a glass matrix. The effectiveness of the immobilization is confirmed by leaching test using the MCC-1 standard.

Keywords: alkali activation, boro-pollucite, cesium immobilization, cold consolidation process, viscous flow sintering.

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Study of Gallium Doped Bioactive Glass Nanoparticles in 2D and 3D Cultivation Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Despite extensive research, the treatment of many cancer diseases is still limited. The field of biomaterials, especially nanomaterials, shows great potential for therapeutic use in oncology. 3D spheroids, which mimic *in vivo* environment more closely than traditional 2D cell culture models, can better predict the effectiveness and toxicity of drugs. Nanoparticles containing gallium show potential for the treatment of different tumors since released gallium can disturb several cell signaling processes, which ultimately results in the activation of programmed cell death. In the present work, we investigated the effect of gallium-containing mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles on the survival of different tumor cell lines in 2D and 3D cultivation conditions. Identifying changes in cell viability of tumor cells can significantly contribute to understanding gallium's effect on cells and highlight the potential of present nanoparticles for use in the treatment of specific cancer diseases.

Keywords: 3D spheroids, cell viability, gallium nanoparticles, tumor cells

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Effect of the benign solvent system produced with different FA/AA ratios on the fabrication of PCL, chitosan and κ -carrageenan electrospun nanofibers

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ABSTRACT

The use of degradable natural biopolymers with different electrostatic nature offers a notable set of beneficial characteristics when they are intended to be applied in various fields of biomedicine. Particularly, their incorporation into polymer formulations for the fabrication of fibrous systems by electrospinning has aroused great interest [1, 2]. In this work, composite fiber mats were successfully produced using poly(epsilon caprolactone) (PCL) as the main polymer component in combination with two polysaccharides, one polycationic and one polyanionic [ref]. Benign solvent systems based on different ratios of formic acid (FA) and acetic acid (AA) were used to produce polymer solutions containing PCL, chitosan (CS), and κ -carrageenan (κ -C). This benign mixture was considered to avoid a negative response caused by the use of toxic solvents. Not only the FA/AA ratio played a key role in the resulting properties of the fiber mats, but also the addition of κ -C was shown to enhance and facilitate the fabrication of electrospun fibers made of PCL and CS, as reported by Liverani et al., [Liverani]. Furthermore, the presence of κ -C increased the stability of the polymer solution, reducing the amount of waste derived from the electrospinning process. Three different FA/AA ratios were studied (3:7, 1:1 and 7:3, respectively), in all cases the produced fiber mats were shown to have average fiber diameters on the nanoscale. Physicochemical and mechanical characterization demonstrated that the 7:3 ratio led to the most promising properties, increasing the wettability and Young's modulus of the resulting fiber mats. To study the shelf-life capacity of the polymer solution, the 7:3 ratio was chosen to be stored at -20 °C for 30 days before fabricating the fibers. The bioactivity assessment in simulated body fluid (SBF) revealed that only those fibers produced from the FA/AA mixture in a 7:3 ratio presented a possible bioactive response due to the formation of a layer of particles on the surface of the fibrous systems. In conclusion, composite fiber mats produced using the highest ratio of formic acid proved their suitability as potential candidates for bone tissue engineering and wound healing applications.

Keywords: Benign solvent system, κ -Carrageenan, Chitosan, Electrospun nanofibers, FA/AA ratio, PCL.

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Cerium and Zinc-Substituted Nanoscale Hydroxyapatite for Bone Tissue Engineering

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ABSTRACT

Calcium phosphate-based biomaterials have a long history of clinical use in bone tissue engineering applications. Among these materials, nanoscale hydroxyapatite (nHA) has gained significant recognition due to its exceptional biocompatibility, biological properties, and ability to serve as a filler material in developing bioinspired composite systems. Zinc and cerium, both possessing advantageous features, such as promoting osteogenesis and exhibiting antibacterial activity, have emerged as promising candidates for enhancing the functionality of these materials. In this study, we used a wet precipitation method to synthesize nanoscale hydroxyapatite particles with calcium partially substituted by zinc or cerium at concentrations of 5 and 10 mol%. The synthesized particles were characterised using various techniques, including SEM, XRD, FTIR, and XPS. The morphology analysis revealed that all samples exhibited rod-like shapes with thicknesses ranging from 20 to 30 nm and lengths between 100 and 200 nm. XRD analysis demonstrated that the samples primarily consisted of hydroxyapatite crystals. The samples with 5 and 10 mol% zinc or cerium substitution showed similar results to undoped hydroxyapatite samples in both XRD and FTIR studies. To assess the biocompatibility of these materials, cytotoxicity tests were conducted using MG-63 (human osteoblast-like cell line) and ST-2 (mouse stromal cell line) at concentrations up to 4 mg/mL. The results indicated that Zn and Ce-substituted nHA did not exhibit cytotoxic effects on MG-63 cells even at the highest concentration tested (4 mg/mL). However, these particles caused some level of cytotoxicity against ST-2 cells, but only at concentrations exceeding 0.5 mg/mL. The antibacterial properties of these materials were evaluated against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, showing promising results. This study demonstrates that nanoscale hydroxyapatite particles with zinc or cerium substitution can be considered attractive bioactive filler materials for multifunctional bone tissue engineering applications. These materials exhibit excellent biocompatibility, making them suitable candidates for further exploration in developing advanced biomaterials for bone regeneration and related biomedical applications.

Keywords: antibacterial effect, biocompatibility, cerium, hydroxyapatite, nanoparticles, zinc

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The influence of morphology and topography of Chitosan-Zn complex fiber mats on the viability and attachment of stromal cells and mouse fibroblasts

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ABSTRACT

Electrospinning has emerged as a promising technique for creating fibrous materials that mimic the extracellular matrix, holding significant potential for therapeutic wound healing applications. This study focuses on investigating the influence of fiber topography on cell attachment, particularly in conjunction with biochemical cues. Four distinct biodegradable fiber mats were synthesized, including chitosan and chitosan-zinc complex (ChiZn) fibers with varying diameters, both in the nano and micron-sized ranges. The ChiZn complex was synthesized via the in-situ precipitation method, ensuring a homogeneous distribution of zinc. Subsequently, ChiZn was blended with polyethylene oxide (PEO) to facilitate electrospinning in a benign solvent system and crosslinked with glutaraldehyde vapor. Characterization of the fiber mats was performed using various techniques, including X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscopy (SEM)/energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), and atomic force microscopy (AFM). The structural integrity, morphology, and roughness of the fibers were comprehensively assessed. Cell viability, adhesion, and proliferation studies were conducted using stromal cells (ST-2) and mouse fibroblasts (MEF) to evaluate the biocompatibility of the fiber mats. Higher cell viability was observed on mats composed of nanosized fibers, highlighting the influence of topography on cellular responses. The early attachment and spread of cells were examined by SEM after 1- and 7-days of incubation, revealing distinctive cell behaviors on nanosized and micron-sized fibers. The results confirm that topographical features and surface chemistry play an important role in material-cell interactions. Furthermore, the observed synergistic effects between topography and biochemical cues open up areas for future research, paving the way for the development of advanced biomaterials tailored for optimal cell response and tissue regeneration.

Keywords: chitosan, cell attachment, electrospinning.

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Development of (F, Si) carbon-based film on glass substrate by Plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) for self-cleaning applications

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ABSTRACT

Fabricating hydrophobic surfaces with a low friction coefficient is an ideal approach for increasing the performance of self-cleaning glasses and solar cells. To this end, plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) was used to fabricate (F, Si) carbon, diamond-like carbon (DLC), Si-doped DLC, and F-doped DLC films on a glass substrate. Raman spectroscopy revealed that the Si-DLC film has the highest sp^3/sp^2 ratio of carbon hybridization, and the F-DLC film has the lowest. As confirmed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), SiC can be formed by incorporating silicon into the DLC layer. In addition, CF_2 and CF_3 groups are created in fluorinated coatings such as F-DLC and (F, Si) carbon films. Due to the high surface concentration of CF_2 and CF_3 , the (F, Si) carbon film was the most hydrophobic. Nano-scratch and nanoindentation tests were used to analyse the nanomechanical behaviour of the films. While the (F, Si) carbon film had the lowest coefficient of friction, the Si-DLC film demonstrated the highest adhesion strength. Therefore, the Si-DLC film was deposited as a sub-layer of the (F, Si) carbon film to improve the adhesion of the film to the substrate. The highly durable hydrophobic (F, Si) carbon film fabricated in this work has excellent potential for use in self-cleaning applications.

Keywords: Carbon, Plasma, Fluorine, Hydrophobicity, Tribology.

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Preparation and optimisation of YSZ and $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ granules with embedded YSZ whiskers via spray drying

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, gas turbines and diesel engines are equipped with thermal barrier coatings (TBCs) to insulate against hot gases and improve their performance and efficiency. As a result, the critical goal for future turbine engines is to create new TBC materials that have a prolonged lifespan, minimal thermal conductivity, and can withstand extremely high temperatures. Ceramic materials are commonly used for TBCs and must meet specific requirements, such as low heat conductivity, phase stability at both room and operating temperatures, and resistance to sintering at high temperatures [1]. Commercial granules are the preferred material for creating TBC layers. However, spray drying allows the creation of granules with a non-commercial composition, excellent flowability, precise size distribution, and adjustable morphology [2]. The present work involves the creation of TBC coatings using spray-dried granules with various compositions (Yttria-stabilised zirconia (YSZ), YSZ+YSZ whiskers (W), and $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ (LC)+W). The first step was to optimise the suspension parameter for the spray drying process by adjusting the solid loading (30–75 wt.% of YSZ) and binder amount (1–5 wt.% polyvinyl alcohol PVA). The size of the granules was mostly affected by the solid loading of YSZ powder, while the optimum results were obtained by using 75 wt.% YSZ powder and 1 wt.% PVA. In the subsequent phase of the project, YSZ whiskers were added to YSZ and LC powders as a reinforcement to create composite granules that can flow smoothly for producing single- and double-layer TBC coatings. After the process of spray drying, YSZ whiskers were adequately integrated into both powders, and the granules took on a spherical shape.

Keywords: granules, spray drying, suspensions

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Multifunctional Smart Composite Coatings for Corrosion Protection and Monitoring

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ABSTRACT

The world is moving towards green technologies and sustainable economic growth; therefore, there is a strong need to maintain the value and utility of manufactured assets such as vehicles, infrastructure, equipment and consumer goods as high as possible and for the longest possible period. This work aims to develop innovative multifunctional composite coatings for the detection and prevention of the corrosion of metallic structures in high-performance applications throughout their life cycle. Corrosion-resistant coatings protect metallic structures against degradation by disengaging them from the surrounding environments. The main protection mechanisms include physical barrier, galvanic protection and passivation of the substrates. The major limitations of effective corrosion protection systems are their stability, maintenance cost and service life. Composite coatings combining effective corrosion protection with corrosion detection can be used to overcome the limitations of current systems. We propose to develop multifunctional composite coatings by integrating passive barrier properties, active corrosion inhibitor release and nanoparticles-guided corrosion monitoring ability into a single composite system. The durability and longevity of the coatings will be achieved by using eco-friendly materials and considering the interfacial adhesion strength between the substrate/composite and their surrounding environments. The long-term corrosion protection ability will be achieved through the synergistic effects of the passive barrier properties of the matrix and the stimuli-responsive release of corrosion inhibitors. The presence of nanoparticles will help detect the onset of metallic corrosion based on either magnetic flux leakage measurements or visual response when the coating is damaged. These durable and biocompatible composite systems will ensure minimum cost and environmental impacts consistent with desired properties. The coatings are expected to facilitate the protection of larger areas in the aerospace, offshore and automobile sectors.

Keywords: Corrosion protection; Self-healing coatings; Corrosion inhibitors; Adhesion strength; Corrosion monitoring; Stimuli-responsive release; Nanocarriers.

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PEO/Sol-gel duplex coatings on AZ31B alloy for degradable implant applications

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ABSTRACT

Magnesium (Mg)-based materials, utilized as a novel generation of orthopedic implant materials, are anticipated to replace permanent implants due to their mechanical characteristics comparable to bone and total biodegradability within the human body. The therapeutic application of Mg-based materials is hindered due to their rapid breakdown under physiological environments, not their biocompatibility. To overcome this limitation, several methods have been utilized to control the breakdown rate of magnesium, such as the incorporation of alloying elements, surface treatment, and surface modification or coating.

This study involved the incorporation of various additives, namely, sodium silicate (SO), trisodium orthoborate (BO), and sodium bicarbonate (CO), into the base electrolyte consisting of sodium hydroxide and trisodium phosphate (PO) with the aim. To induce the formation of protective oxide layers on the AZ31B magnesium-based alloy by the PEO (plasma electrolytic oxidation) technique. The PEO coatings were examined and characterized in terms of their morphology, chemical composition, and phase composition using scanning electron microscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, and X-ray diffraction analysis, respectively. The evaluation of the coatings' corrosion performance was conducted by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy using Hanks and 3.5% NaCl solutions. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) examination indicated the impact of the electrolyte on the pore structure of the coatings, with the mean pore sizes of 0.7 μm for CO, 1.2 μm for BO, 1.4 μm for SO, and 1.6 μm for PO. The thickness of the coating was not influenced by the modification of the electrolyte solution. The corrosion resistance of CO coatings was shown to be superior in both NaCl and Hanks solutions, as confirmed by their electrochemical behavior. The enhanced resistance was related to the smaller pore size of the coating. To enhance the bioactivity of the CO coatings, a hybrid 58S sol was applied as a topcoat using dip-coating. The immersion investigations on these duplex coatings have demonstrated the bioactive coating's capacity to form apatite layers which was confirmed by SEM.

Keywords: Bioactivity; Sol-gel; Dip coating; Control degradation; Plasma electrolytic oxidation

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Understanding the phase transformation behavior of – HEOs under various conditions of sintering

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ABSTRACT

High entropy ceramic oxides (HEOs) represent a cutting-edge frontier of advanced research in the field of materials science and engineering. These materials have generated considerable research interest because of their novel intrinsic properties and significant potential for application in various fields. A single-phase high-entropy ceramic rare earth phosphor with the composition $(Y_{0.2}Ce_{0.2}Dy_{0.2}Sm_{0.2}La_{0.2})O_{2-\delta}$ was prepared by combustion synthesis. X-ray powder diffraction and scanning electron microscopy were performed on the synthesized sample to analyze the phase composition and morphological features of the powder. Subsequently, the powders were sintered by conventional pressure less sintering, spark plasma sintering (SPS), and vacuum sintering to prepare high density materials. The spark plasma sintering of the samples at temperature above 1600°C in the vacuum and under reducing conditions resulted in oxygen depletion. As a result, phase transformation from cubic to monocline phase was observed. The phase transformation was found to be reversible to cubic structure was formed again after annealing the sample at 1200°C in the air.

Keywords: Phase transformation, Functional ceramics, High-entropy ceramic, Spark plasma sintering.

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Humidity-Induced Curing and Anti-Corrosion Properties of Polyorganosilazane/GPTMS Coating on AA2024-T3

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ABSTRACT

The influence of relative humidity on the curing process and anti-corrosion properties of a novel coating composed of polyorganosilazane and 3-glycidyloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTMS) functionalized silica was studied. The coating was applied by dip-coating on AA2024-T3 aluminum alloy surfaces. The coating was then subjected to various relative humidity levels ranging from 15% to 80%, subsequent curing at 120°C for 2 hours, yielding a transparent, crack-free surface with a thickness of 15–17 μm. The coating's exposure to humidity caused the hydrolysis of Si-H, Si-NH, and Si-N-Si bonds through reactions with water vapor, leading to the formation of silanols. The incorporation of ethoxysilane (SiOEt) groups facilitated these reactions, offering control over the coating's reactivity and promoting cross-linking among polymer chains. This process resulted in a significant reinforcement of the coating's internal structure, enhancing the corrosion resistance of AA2024-T3 in a saline environment. The exposure to the environment with 40% relative humidity significantly enhanced the coating's anti-corrosion properties, as quantified by potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements, revealing an initial impedance value of 10⁹ ohm·cm² in a 3.5% NaCl. The prepared coatings show potential to enhance the durability and reliability of aluminum alloy surfaces for various industrial applications.

Keywords: AA2024-T3, anti-corrosion, coatings, GPTMS, humidity, polyorganosilazane

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Study of thermal behaviour glasses in system $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Yb}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Er}_2\text{O}_3$

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ABSTRACT

The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-RE}_2\text{O}_3$ glasses, where RE can be Y, Yb, or La, are considered promising materials due to their impressive mechanical, chemical, thermal, and optical properties. Additionally, these glasses have a higher ability to absorb optically active ions than their crystalline counterparts and Yb^{3+} doped aluminate materials are particularly useful for modern laser applications because of their simple electronic structure, low quantum defect, longer lifetime, and broader bandwidth of the emission lines. Moreover, Yb^{3+} ions also have the ability to enhance the emission of Er^{3+} ions in materials. However, the production of these systems is both financially and technologically demanding, which limits their use. The solution to this issue is to prepare these glasses using flame synthesis (FS). Such prepared glass microspheres can then be turned into larger pieces of glass or glass ceramics through hot-press (HP) sintering. Therefore, is important to determine the HP conditions by analyzing the thermal behavior of the glasses.

In this work, three samples of glasses with 62.5 mol. % Al_2O_3 and 37.5 mol. % Yb_2O_3 , doped by 2, 6 and 10 mol. % of Er^{3+} were prepared by a combination of the sol-gel Pechini method and FS. The thermal behaviour of prepared glasses was studied using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in temperature interval 30 – 1100 °C and heating rates: 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 °C.min⁻¹. The crystallization kinetics was examined using three methods: Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS), Ozawa-Flynn-Wall (OFW) and Friedman, activation energies E_A and frequency factors A were determined. The highest E_A value was calculated for the sample with 10 mol. % Er^{3+} addition. Subsequently, isothermal experiments ($T=914$ °C, $t=40$ min.) were performed. The XRD analysis of crystallised samples confirms pure YbAG phase crystallisation. SEM study of the morphology of crystallised samples showed the presence of cubic YbAG crystals in the whole volume of the sample. Based on these results, bulk crystallization can be expected in all glasses, which makes these systems suitable for preparing larger pieces of glass-ceramics by controlled crystallization.

Keywords: thermal analysis, crystallization kinetic, aluminate glasses

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Preparation of polymer-derived ceramic coatings with $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ and different types of glasses

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ABSTRACT

Polymer-derived ceramics (PDCs) is an appropriate material for preparing protective coatings due to their excellent oxidation and corrosion resistance at elevated temperatures. However, the primary challenge of this approach is the remarkable shrinkage during polymer-to-ceramic conversion [1]. One way to compensate for high volume shrinkage is to add suitable filler particles to the coating slurry. In this work, $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ (LZ) powder has been selected as a promising filler material for PDC coatings because of its excellent thermal stability, high melting point (2300 °C), and low thermal conductivity [2]. For this purpose, LZ powder was heat-treated at 1400 °C for 6 h, and some properties, such as powder morphology, crystal structure, and thermal stability, were investigated after high-temperature treatment. A single pyrochlore phase of LZ was detected by XRD after annealing at 1400 °C. The thermal behaviour of LZ powder was investigated by DSC and TGA in the temperature range of 25–1300 °C. Four types of glasses, including $\text{BaO-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$ (BAS), $\text{B}_2\text{O}_3\text{-CaO-SiO}_2$ (CBS), $\text{BaO-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-La}_2\text{O}_3\text{-B}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$ (BALBS), and $\text{BaO-ZnO-MgO-B}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$ (BZMBS), were synthesised to be incorporated into coating compositions. Then, the coating systems, consisting of a Durazane 2250 bond coat and a top coat (Durazane 1800 + LZ filler + glass), were prepared. A double-layer PDC coating was applied to stainless steel substrates. In this work, four top coat slurries containing various glasses were prepared to compare the performance of different glasses in coating composition. After pyrolysis in air at 900 °C, the XRD results showed the presence of a single LZ phase in the BAS glass/LZ-filled coating. Based on the results obtained from SEM, the composite coating containing BAS glass and LZ filler was crack-free and dense; only a few small pores were observed.

Keywords: Fillers, Organosilicon Precursor, PDC coatings, Pyrolysis, Solid state reaction, Thermal stability

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Corrosion performance and wear resistance of LDH reinforced Si-hydroxyapatite nanocomposite coating deposited on Ni-Ti alloy

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ABSTRACT

The replacement of bone tissue for metallic implants has gained special interest in the last decades. However, there are implant that suffer corrosion, fatigue fracture, wear and incompatibility with host tissue, aspects that can be solved by superficial modification of the metallic substrates [1]. Particularly, inorganic ceramic coatings such as hydroxyapatite (HAp, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) have been widely employed to improve the incompatibility [2]. Nevertheless, the brittle nature and poor strength of HAp coating are a problem, especially when the implant need to work under load-bearing conditions. Therefore, the incorporation of nanoparticles as secondary bioactive fillers enhance their characteristics [3].

Thus, this work is based on the preparation of Sr/Ga nanoparticles by LDH and their incorporation in silicon substituted HAp coating as an active/passive filler. The nanoparticles would act as drug/ion release to increase the bioactivity and also to block the corrosive species and avoid the corrosion of the metallic substrate. For this purpose, Sr/Ga LDH nanoparticles has been synthesized using co-precipitation and ion exchange method. Then, surface of Ti substrates has been pre-treated by anodizing to increase the corrosion resistance and adhesion properties. The morphology, topology, composition, and electrochemical properties of the passivated surfaces have been characterized.

Finally, a Si-HAp coating loaded with Sr/Ga LDH nanoparticles has been electrophoretically deposited on anodized samples. The release ability of LDHs make them a desirable candidate as bioactive additive for bone regeneration. The flake morphology of these nanoparticles can enhance the barrier performance and the toughness of the HAp coating [4]. The effect of LDH incorporation on the anticorrosion behavior of Si-HAp coated nitinol samples was studied by polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The lowest amount of nickel release was observed for LDH @ Si-HAp coated nitinol samples.

Keywords: Nitinol, Hydroxyapatite, Layered double hydroxide, surface modification, Corrosion, anodization.

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Different Approaches of Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ Co-doped Oxyfluoride Transparent Glass-Ceramics in Relation to Up-Conversion Optical Properties

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ABSTRACT

Transparent oxyfluoride glass-ceramics (TGCs) that incorporate rare earth ions (RE³⁺) exhibit considerable potential for use in photoluminescence up-conversion and down-conversion [1]. The Li⁺ ion has been proposed as a viable alternative to the Na⁺/K⁺ ion for the formation of scheelite-tetragonal crystals [2]. LiYF₄ crystals are favourable matrices for trivalent RE³⁺ ions due to their ability to accommodate isomorphic substitution of Y³⁺ by other RE³⁺ ions. This is mostly attributed to the comparable ionic radius of these ions, which does not significantly impact the lattice structure. Moreover, the presence of Li⁺ ions can induce crystal field distortion and promote asymmetry around RE³⁺ ions because of its smaller cationic radius, hence leading to an increase in emission intensity [2,3].

The present investigation involved the preparation of 40 SiO₂-25 Al₂O₃-18 Li₂O-7 LiF-(10-x-y) YF₃-x ErF₃-y YbF₃ (x = 0, 0.1, 0.5; y = 0, 0.4, 2, 4) glasses using melt-quenching technique. Three distinct methods were employed in the preparation of TGCs. (1) The bulk glasses underwent a thermal treatment at 540 °C above glass transition temperature (T_g+35 °C) for 20, 40 and 80 h [4]. (2) The glass powder, 63 μm < x < 100 μm was compressed under a pressure of 92 MPa for 5 min using spark plasma sintering (SPS). Subsequently, it was subjected to the first stage of sintering temperatures for 20 min under a pressure of 20-30 MPa. (3) Hot isostatic pressing (HIP) was used, where the glass powder was directly compressed and heat-treated by the pressing mould under a pressure of 20-30 MPa. This process occurred at the end of the sintering stage without further holding time. According to route (1), XRD analysis revealed the production of LiYF₄ and LiAlSiO₄ nanocrystals after a 20 h thermal treatment at 540 °C. The treatment duration was increased to 80 h, which increased the UC luminescence yield while decreasing the Red to Green ratio (R/G) emission intensity. The glass-ceramic products were transparent (%T) in the near-infrared (NIR) and visible spectral regions due to the nano-sized crystals, with %T retaining around 85% and 75%, respectively, after 20 h treatment. However, because of the growth in crystal size and crystalline content percentage, the visible window transparency decreased, with %T dropping to roughly 50% after 80 h. The effect of Yb³⁺ co-doping on up-conversion (UC) luminescence in glass-ceramics was investigated and compared to parent glasses, confirming that Yb³⁺ ions were also a key factor for facilitating up-conversion via energy transfer (ET), leading to a higher luminescence yield than in Er³⁺ single doped glass-ceramics and tuning of R/G intensities. The initial findings from the SPS and HIP experiments demonstrated a significant increase in the quantity of LiYF₄ NPs, around 27-33 %, in the TGC samples. The optimization of heating temperatures, pressure, and holding periods is crucial for achieving many objectives, including the elimination of carbon diffusion content in samples, preservation of transparency, and enhancement of luminescence.

To avoid the presence of unwanted phases in TGC (e.g. LiAlSiO₄), another approach to prepare TGC is to pack LiYbF₄:Er@LiYF₄ core-shell nanoparticles (NPs) into duran glass with subsequent sintering using either SPS or HIP to produce bulk samples. The NPs were synthesized by solvo-thermal decomposition method at 300 °C for 90 min, with oleic acid acting as an anchoring agent [5]. XRD revealed the presence of LiYbF₄ and LiF in the as-synthesized core samples. The washing procedure is currently being optimized in order to effectively remove the Oleic Acid, which as a carbon source reduces the transparency of the sintered samples.

Keywords: lithium fluoride, oxyfluoride, photoluminescence, rare earth ions, transparent glass-ceramics.

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Effect of Co and B co-doped mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles on various cell lines

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ABSTRACT

To enhance the multifaceted utility of bioactive glasses in biomedical materials, this study presents a novel approach by co-doping mesoporous bioactive glasses with cobalt (Co) and boron (B) ions. This research aims to produce a highly versatile biomaterial that combines mesoporous bioactive glasses' inherent biocompatibility and osteoinductive properties with the therapeutic potential offered by Co and B ions.

Co and B co-doped mesoporous bioactive glasses were synthesized through a sol-gel method, allowing precise control over composition and structural characteristics [1]. Comprehensive material characterization techniques, including X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), were employed to evaluate the physicochemical properties of the synthesized materials. Accordingly, the bioactivity assessment in simulated body fluid (SBF) for 14 days under physiological conditions confirmed the formation of hydroxyapatite-like crystals.

Figure: a) SEM micrographs of representative sample, b) SEM micrographs of representative sample after bioactivity testing with creating of hydroxyapatite-like crystals.

Both cobalt and boron are essential in trace amounts for various biochemical processes and can induce a multitarget effect, especially on angiogenesis, by activating mRNA expression of pro-angiogenic proteins like vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGFA). The controlled and sustained release of these ions from the bioactive biomaterials is essential to ensure therapeutic benefits without toxicity [2], [3]. Our study delved into crucial *in vitro* biocompatibility assessments, employing a variety of cell lines to gauge the potential of these materials for broad biomedical applications. By testing on specific cell lines related to certain diseases, we can evaluate the nanoparticles' potential as targeted therapeutic agents. On the other hand testing on various cell lines helps understand how these nanoparticles behave in different cellular contexts, which can influence their application. Therefore, the cell viability tests were conducted using the following cell lines: MG63 (osteosarcoma cell line), ST-2 (mouse bone marrow stromal cell line), T98G (human glioblastoma cell line), SHYS-5Y (human neuroblastoma cell line), A549 (human lung carcinoma cell line), HT-29 (human colorectal adenocarcinoma cell line) and BxPC-3 (human pancreatic adenocarcinoma cell line).

The dual dopants also contributed to enhancing the antimicrobial properties, further broadening the scope of their potential biomedical applications.

Keywords: boron, cell lines, cobalt, mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles, therapeutic ions

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Robocasting of Boron doped S53P4-based bioactive scaffolds

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ABSTRACT

Including therapeutic ions like boron allows customization of bioactive glass performance. This enables the materials to meet the demands of scaffold-like structures that closely mimic natural bone properties in tissue engineering. Robocasting, a prominent extrusion-based additive manufacturing (AM) technique, is employed in this study to fabricate three-dimensional scaffolds. These scaffolds are designed with controlled pore architecture, a crucial feature for promoting bone tissue regeneration. To achieve this, we utilized a composite ink consisting of B-doped S53P4 bioactive glass and a gelatine-based binder. The bioactive glasses utilized as feedstock material were fabricated using the melt-quenching method and ground to a particle size of less than 40 microns. The scaffolds prepared through the robocasting process were then burn-out and sintered, resulting in a moderate shrinkage of around 30%. Comprehensive analysis of the scaffolds was performed to determine their structural integrity and composition, ultimately improving our knowledge of their possible uses in tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: Robocasting, Scaffold, Bioactive Glass, Bone Tissue Engineering

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Preparation and characterization of basaltic glass-ceramic composites

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ABSTRACT

An attempt was made to synthesize a novel glass-ceramic material and a series of composite materials, utilizing basalt rock sourced from Serbia, specifically the Vrelo locality, as the primary raw material. The overarching goal of this research endeavor is to engineer innovative materials poised for versatile applications across various industries. Within this study, two distinctive composite materials are planned to be synthesized.

The initial composite incorporates a high-temperature-resistant standardized steel-wire mesh, which is readily available in the commercial market and seamlessly integrated into the basalt matrix. Meanwhile, the second composite incorporates mine tailings originating from Bor, Serbia, exemplifying a conscientious approach to sustainable material development. Both composites underwent a meticulously orchestrated manufacturing process involving the fusion and casting of basalt into molds, resulting in the formation of a glass-like substance. Subsequently, the cast glass was subjected to heat treatment at temperatures optimized through Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) analysis, with a uniform retention time of 1 hour for each sample.

In the case of samples containing mine tailings, the primary basalt material was blended with varying weight ratios of mine tailings. Conversely, for the samples featuring the steel-wire mesh, the basalt melt was cast directly over the integrated mesh within the mold, culminating in the creation of a composite material reminiscent of a sandwich structure, with the steel-wire mesh serving as the central component.

Thorough chemical and mechanical assessments of the resulting materials have underscored their suitability for a wide spectrum of industrial applications. This research augments the materials science landscape, promising innovation and enhanced versatility that can be harnessed across diverse industrial sectors. In a world increasingly focused on sustainable practices, the incorporation of mine tailings and high-temperature-resistant components such as steel-wire mesh highlights the potential for environmentally responsible material development, further advancing the paradigm of sustainable innovation in materials science.

Keywords: glass-ceramic, basalt, composite materials

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Fabrication and characterization of bismuth-doped bioactive glasses for tissue engineering: from micro to nano

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ABSTRACT

Background: The development of bioactive glasses (BGs) has been important for advanced healthcare applications since Larry Hench discovered the first BGs more than 50 years ago. BGs exhibit potential for osteogenesis, vascularization, as well as antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects. Moreover, the introduction of mesoporosity leads to more fruitful functions, for instance, mesoporous bioactive glasses (MBGs) have provided interesting possibilities for drug and biomolecular delivery due to their excellent surface area, pore volume and pore size. MBGs can also be combined with trace elements to enhance specific biological functions. In recent times, bismuth has gained attention from researchers for its prospective applications in biomedicine. These include its non-toxic and economical nature, optimal antibacterial properties, and capacity for cancer therapy and biosensing.

Purpose: Development of highly dispersed BiBGs for bone regeneration and wound healing applications.

Methods: BiBGs were prepared by evaporation induced self-assembly (EISA) and sol-gel method, their morphologies and chemical compositions were examined by SEM, EDX, and XRF. Glass crystallization was studied by XRD. Furthermore, the in vitro bioactivity of BiBGs was examined by using the SBF immersion test. Cell culture experiments using normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF) demonstrated their cytocompatibility.

Results and Conclusions: BiMBGs (less than 2000 nm) and BiMBGNs with uniform size (around 200 nm) were prepared. It's worth mentioning that nano BGs are more regular in shape than micron BGs, and the former has obvious mesopore distribution. Good bioactivity was exhibited by the rapid formation of hydroxyapatite by soaking in SBF for 3 days. The cell viability results also demonstrated that BiBGs had good cell viability against NHDF, facilitating the spreading and proliferation of up to 5 mol% of Bi. The newly developed BiBGs in micro/nanoparticles are a promising option for tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: Micro and nano-sized Bioactive glasses, Bismuth, Tissue Engineering

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Preparation and characterization of alkali activated materials from waste glass and industrial waste

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Alkali activated materials, including geopolymers, may represent a solution, but only when minimizing virgin raw materials, like metakaolin and synthetic alkali activators. Among raw materials for sustainable alkali activated materials, glass fractions which cannot be conveniently reused, by remelting, in the manufacturing of original articles, are particularly interesting, since they are mostly already in the form of fine powders, enhancing the reactivity. The current study mainly focus on two variants of waste glass, consisting of boro-alumino-silicate glass and sodalime glass. Alone or mixed with other industrial or natural scraps, after 'mild' alkali activation ^[i], i.e. immersion in NaOH and KOH solution of molarity not exceeding 3M, they form a stable cementitious matrix, according to partial dissolution and condensation reactions. Three different kind of foundry sands deriving from the production of cast iron are used as a filler in different proportions; the leaching test performed on these conglomerates indicates a very good stabilization of any pollutants. Thanks to the collaboration with local factories (Terreal Italia Srl and Bigaran Srl), it is considered the possibility to extend cold consolidated process even to activated sodalime glass, discarded rock wool, and solid inert waste from the bricks polishing and manufacturing. Differently from other samples, in order increase the industrial development, alkaline solution is prepared using a 'mud' (pH=9.5) deriving from the cutting and polishing of clay bricks, instead of distilled water. These variants do not affect the gel stability, as proven by water boiling tests. The new building materials originated from alkali activation, without thermal transformation, finally, exhibit physical and mechanical properties similar to those typical of commercial (fired) bricks. Preliminary studies on the immobilization of brown mud, waste deriving from Bayer sintering process, are on-going: leaching and boiling tests are performed to understand the release of this hazardous waste ^[iii].

Among pozzolanic and volcanic materials can be used as a filler in alkali activated materials based on sodalime glass. The unemployed fraction of grey tuff can be used to produce cold consolidated blocks or highly porous foams using Triton X-100 (C₁₄H₂₂O(C₂H₄O)_n, n=9–10)^[iii]. Moreover, volcanic ash from Mt. Etna, considered nowadays as "municipal waste" residues from road cleaning in European Waste Catalogue ^[iv], can be embedded into glass matrix in different proportion. Both solid samples and foams are manufactured without sintering process. As an end-of-life option, thermal transformation at 950°C can applied on the samples obtained at room temperature, as a possible recycling into second generation components ^[v].

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